

Food Residue Biomass Product as an Alternative Fuel for the Cement Industry

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the production of an Alternative Fuel (AF) for the cement industry from a Food Residue Biomass (FORBI) product, generated from pre-sorted Household Food Waste (HFW). FORBI is generated by drying and shredding the fermentable fraction of HFW collected door-to-door in the Municipality of Halandri, Greece. The key physicochemical properties such as the net calorific value (NCV), the concentration of heavy metals and chlorine are subsequently determined using well-established international standards (EN and ISO). FORBI is evaluated as a potential AF in terms of technical feasibility and environmental impacts. Based on the characterization, FORBI is classified as a non-dangerous waste according to EWC 20 01 08, European Commission Decision 2014/955. According to EN 15359 it is classified as category 3, 2 and 1 with respect to NCV, Cl and Hg respectively. The study concludes that FORBI is a suitable candidate as a secondary fuel for the cement industry, given its high calorific value along with its low humidity and ash content. Challenges for practical implementation include the relatively high chlorine content, the inclusion of alkalis in the cement produced and the reduction of non-thermal NO_x emissions.

Keywords: cement industry, alternative fuel, co-processing, Food Residue Biomass (FORBI).

1. Introduction

The cement industry is one of the most energy-intensive industries, with thermal and electrical energy needs typically accounting for about 40% of the operational costs (European Commission 2013). Clinker production requires considerable energy consumption, since the kiln temperature should exceed 1500°C. According to CEMBUREAU, the European Cement Association, each ton of cement produced typically requires 60 to 130 kg of fuel oil equivalent, depending on the cement type and the kiln technology employed, and about 110 KWh of electrical energy (CEMBUREAU, Iozia, 2011). Furthermore, according to (OECD, 2012) in 2010 the cement industry was responsible for 2,823 million metric tons (Mt) of CO₂ emissions. The Chinese economy itself used more cement in the years 2011-2013 than the USA during the entire 20th century (Smil, 2013). The high cost and environmental impacts of fossil fuel usage have compelled cement manufacturers worldwide to consider the replacement of conventional fuels by AFs. According to Kajaste & Hurme, 2016, the basic driver for managing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) in the cement industry is the growing anthropogenic gas emissions, as well as the increasing global demand for cement. One of the basic options for the reduction of GHG emissions in the cement industry is to partially replace the fossil fuels used in the kilns with alternative and renewable energy sources.

Co-processing of waste contributes to the solution of waste management problems via an environmentally sound, energy recovery option for many waste materials, while at the same time contributing to more eco-efficient cement production (Holcim, 2006). Social, environmental and economic benefits may result from using cement kilns for the management of waste, including a reduced amount of landfilled waste and CO₂ emissions, preventing depletion of fossil fuels and avoiding investment for new waste-to energy facilities (Ecofys, 2017). Utilization of AFs for cement production has received increasing attention in the last twenty years worldwide. Co-combustion of waste in cement kilns has several advantages, such as attaining high temperature (around 1,450°C) and high residence time in an oxygen rich atmosphere, as well as incorporation of ashes in the clinker (preventing the need for fly ash-disposal). Intensive contact of the solid and gas phases ensures absorption and conversion of volatiles, absorption of SO₂ and neutralization of acids (Patel and Chauhan 2014). In the recent years, considerable amounts of fossil fuels have been substituted by AFs.

54 A review of the use of AFs in the cement industry identified the following main of such fuels (Rahman et al, 2015):

- 55 1. Used tyres
- 56 2. Municipal solid waste (MSW)
- 57 3. Spent pot liner (SPL), which is a solid waste generated from the aluminium industry during the manufacture of
58 aluminum metal in electrolytic cells.
- 59 4. MBM (meat and bone meal)
- 60 5. Plastic waste
- 61 6. Sewage sludge
- 62 7. Solvent and spent oil
- 63 8. Agricultural biomass
- 64 9. Others (carpet waste, automobile shredder residues, waste wood, poultry litter, liquefied natural gas, fluff,
65 textile waste, paper residue, packing boxes, livestock manure, oil-soaked rags etc.)

66 Other works indicate similar classes of AFs including residue-based sources, industrial solid wastes, MSW, refuse
67 derived fuel (RDF) (Genon and Brizio 2008) tyres, waste oils and solvents, plastics, textiles and paper waste, biomass,
68 meat and bone meal (MBM), wood chips and wood waste, recycled paper, agricultural waste such as rice husk, sawdust,
69 sewage sludge and biomass crops (Benhalal et al, 2013; Tsiliyannis et al, 2016).

70 The use of AFs in the cement industry offers a wide variety of environmental, social, technical and economic
71 advantages. The cost of the AFs is considerably lower than the cost of the fossil fuels, especially when minimal
72 preparation is needed (Wellington and Dhanjal, 2008). Moreover, the substitution of the fossil fuels used in the cement
73 industry relies on the preservation of non-renewable energy sources and the reduction of waste disposal sites (Trezza
74 and Scian, 2000). This can offer extended social and economic advantages both for local communities and globally.

75 However, switching from conventional to AFs also presents challenges mainly because of differing physicochemical
76 characteristics. Major challenges include poor heat distribution, unstable precalciner operation, blockages in the
77 preheater cyclones, build-ups in the kiln riser ducts, higher SO₂, NO_x and CO emissions and dusty kilns. Moreover, the
78 final clinker composition needs to be taken into account, since the combustion by-products are incorporated into the
79 clinker. Hence, there is an urgent need to address all these challenges, otherwise the benefits derived from using AFs in
80 the cement industry may be overshadowed by impacts and product quality (Chinyama, 2011).

81 Mass recircuting and energy integration render the impacts of AF utilization plant-wide, with direct repercussions on
82 operation and profitability, affecting clinker level, product quality, cost of operation and off-gas emissions, including
83 persistent organic pollutants and metals (Achternbosch et al 2003; Karstensen, K. 2008; Tsiliyannis 2012). As a result,
84 AF pre-processing and preparation is needed for most types of wastes, such as industrial or MSW, in order to comply
85 with technical specifications of cement kilns and operating conditions (Holcim 2006). According to CEMBUREAU, the
86 pre-treatment of the raw materials that will be used as AFs in cement kilns mainly involves homogenization to achieve
87 and maintain the required uniform chemical composition before feeding the kiln system.

88 Greece has the lowest co-processing rate in the EU, with an average fossil fuel substitution of 7%, compared to the EU
89 average of 41% substitution of fossil fuels by AFs derived from waste and biomass (Ecofys 2017). This is due to limited
90 availability of suitable waste for AFs and long licensing procedures. About 88% of the total produced MSW is
91 landfilled and only 11% is recycled. Financial penalties imposed by EU included a ten million euro penalty for failing
92 to comply with the waste framework directives (Ecofys 2017; European Commission 2013).

93 Although, the percentage of MSW is estimated to be around 10% of the total waste generated at EU level (Eurostat
94 2017), appropriate treatment is crucial from a political perspective, since it relates to protection of human and
95 environmental health due to negative effects of inappropriate waste disposal. The biodegradable fraction of MSW and
96 food waste (FW) in particular, is the fraction which is not systematically recycled/valorized. Its diversion from
97 landfilling is considered of utmost importance in the effort to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. FW is expected to rise
98 to about 126 million tons in 2020 in the EU, from about 90 million tons in 2006 (European Commission 2010). Thus,
99 the EU aims to reduce the amount of biodegradable waste landfilled: a maximum 35% of the 1995 quantities are
100 allowed to be landfilled by 2020 (Eurostat 2010; European Commission 2012). It is therefore imperative to develop
101 methods for managing/treating/exploiting the biodegradable fraction of FW that reduce the quantities of landfilled
102 organic matter, utilizing alternative methods and techniques. A potential route to this end is the use of FW as an AF in
103 the cement industry. After drying and shredding, household food waste may be converted to a low-moisture and high
104 calorific value biomass product, called FORBI, which may be then valorized to generate solid, liquid or gaseous fuels
105 and/or high added-value products.

106 The benefits of using MSW and, consequently FORBI as an AF for the cement industry are multiple. As mentioned, a
107 major challenge for using waste derived fuels as AFs in the cement kilns is the variability of the physicochemical
108 characteristics and the lack of homogeneity. FORBI may be highly promising in this respect, since one of its most
109 important advantages is its homogeneity. Moreover, constant availability is ensured by the generated large amounts of
110 FW. The first research efforts on the possibility of using MSW as a source of AFs for the cement industry go back to
111 the late 80s when Dorn, 1977 tried to identify the advantages and disadvantages of exploiting MSW as AF in cement
112 industry. Later on, many research papers focused on this potential utilization of MSW (i.e. Haley, 1990; Garg et al,

113 2009; Genon and Brizio, 2007). Alternative routes for utilization of waste derived AFs include reuse in energy
114 production, however most of them focused on the RDF, which is a fraction of the MSW different than the
115 biodegradable kitchen waste studied in the present work. The advantages and limitations of FORBI are assessed, in
116 comparison with other AFs, currently in use by the cement industry.

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118 1.1 Implementation of Alternatives for the Recovery of Added Value Materials

119 The present work is a research work within the framework of a Horizon 2020 project called Waste4Think, which
120 proposes source separation and separate collection of the HFW in the Municipality of Halandri, aiming to evaluate this
121 material as potential feedstock for the valorization of alternatives for the recovery of added-value products. Eco-
122 innovative solutions which will be employed in the Municipality also includes: IT tools, apps for citizens, educational
123 material and serious games, tools for citizens and social actions.

124 In order to increase the eco-sustainability of FW management, it is necessary to exploit renewable by-products
125 generated from FW. Nevertheless, the use of by-products is still in its infancy due the necessity to invest in research and
126 new recovery technologies, the costs of which are still higher than landfill taxes. The exploitation of the generated
127 biomass product (FORBI) from FW will be based on collaboration between research and industry for the adaptation and
128 use of already existing technologies and plants for the recovery of by-products.

129 The HFW in Halandri collected from almost 1000 citizens, twice a week. Participants have been provided with 30 L
130 portable household bins and biodegradable bags made of starch, while the filled bags are deposited in locked 120 L
131 bins, proximally located. Residents handle in this manner only kitchen FW such as cooked FW, fruit, vegetable, used
132 tissue paper (cellulose), except for bones and fluids. The 120 L bins are collected by a truck, which will in the future be
133 fueled by biogas (bio CNG) produced from FORBI, in a circular economy approach (Fig. 1).

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136 **Figure 1** Collection, Drying and Shredding of HFW in Halandri, Greece, ([https://left.gr/news/waste4think-ena-pilotiko-programma-](https://left.gr/news/waste4think-ena-pilotiko-programma-toy-dimoy-halandrioy)
137 [toy-dimoy-halandrioy](https://left.gr/news/waste4think-ena-pilotiko-programma-toy-dimoy-halandrioy)).

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139 The collected material is then transferred for drying and shredding to a specially designed unit (Fig. 2). The material is
140 heat-treated (92-98°C) and shredded in a dryer/shredder, in order to generate FORBI.

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144 **Figure 2** A. Halandri's pilot plant B. Dryer/Shredder, C. Produced Food Residue Biomass product FORBI. (Papadopoulou et al
145 2017).

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147 FORBI is a valuable raw material that may be used for: the production of biogas (Hydrogen, Methane and HYTHANE),
 148 compost, animal feed, bioethanol, electricity, pellets, activated carbon and an AF for the cement industry (Fig. 3)
 149 (Papadopoulou et al 2017).
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 152 **Figure 3** Alternatives for the recovery of added-value products (Papadopoulou et al 2017).
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154 **2. Materials and Methods**

155 In order to assess the suitability of FORBI as an AF its physical, chemical and thermal characteristics were analyzed.
 156 The most important parameters are: calorific value, chloride, humidity and toxicity of the AF (Table 1 and Table 2).
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Table 1 Main characteristics of FORBI

Parameters	Results
Humidity (% w/w)	1.3
NCV (MJ/Kg)	17.92
Chloride (% w/w d)	0.50
Hg (% w/w)	n.d*

159 *not detected
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161 The primary objective was the study and design of pilot-scale waste-management solutions aiming at reducing the final
 162 waste volumes landfilled. The final objective is scaling up to support a larger population. Drying and shredding of
 163 collected waste was performed in a GAIA GC-300 dryer/shredder machine (Fig. 4). Typical processing time was 9
 164 hours, yielding a product with humidity lower than 10% w/w down to 1.3% w/w. Preprocessing of the laboratory
 165 specimen was conducted according to the standard (EN 15443 2011). The specimen mass was reduced by *quartering*. A
 166 total of four sub-samples were characterized so as to check the homogeneity of FORBI. The granularity of the specimen
 167 was measured with a Retsch AS 200 vibratory sieve shaker (Fig. 4) and was found to be below 4 mm. For subsequent
 168 analyses the granularity was reduced to below 1mm using a Retsch SM 200 cutting mill (Fig. 4).
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172 **Figure 4** A. GAIA GC-300 Dryer/Shredder B. Retsch AS 200 vibratory sieve shaker and C. Retsch SM 200 cutting mill.

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174 **2.1 Experiments and Standards**

175 The parameters required by Annex A of EN 15359:2011 for the characterization and classification of FORBI as a
176 secondary solid fuel were determined (EN 15359 2011). Direct and elemental analyses, as well as analysis of heavy
177 metals, determination of NCV, of gross calorific value (GCV) and of the bulk density were conducted. In addition, the
178 humidity, concentration of ash, volatile compounds and the fixed carbon were determined by direct analysis. The fixed
179 carbon was evaluated by subtracting the ash and volatiles from the total mass of the sample. The elemental analysis of
180 the sample involved the determination of carbon (C), oxygen (O), nitrogen (N), hydrogen (H), sulfur (S) and chlorine
181 (Cl). The parameters and corresponding standards are given in Table 2.

182
183 **Table 2** Standards used in the analysis of FORBI

Parameter	Measurement standard
Humidity	EN 15414-3:2011
Ash	EN 15403:2011
Volatile compounds	EN 15402:2011
Bulk density	EN 15401:2010
Calorific value	EN 15400:2011
Metals (As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, K, Mn, Na, Ni, P, Pb, Sb, Tl, V, Zn)	EPA 200.7
F, Cl, S	EN 15408:2011
C, H, N	EN 15407:2011
O	ISO 16993

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185 **3. Results and Discussion**

186 The experimental results are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5 together with those of conventional and other AFs. Values for
187 SRF, RDF and coal were obtained from the literature (Wagland et al 2016; Casado et al 2016; Akdag 2016) and were
188 converted to dry-matter-basis equivalents according to (ISO 16993 2015).

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Table 3 Direct analysis of FORBI, SRF, RDF, coal and petcoke.

	Humidity (%)	Ash (%)¹	Volatiles (%)¹	Fixed carbon (%)¹
FORBI	1.1-1.4	8.0-8.7	75.3-78.1	13.2-16.4
SRF (Wagland 2016)	3.0	11.4	82.1	6.5
RDF (Wagland 2016)	30.4	23.3	66.2	10.5
Coal (Wagland 2016)	6.2	12.2	35.2	52.7
Petcoke (Akdag 2016)	7	0.7	12.1	87.4

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¹dry matter basis

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It follows from the data in Table 3, that FORBI exhibits high homogeneity, manifesting the effectiveness of the particular dryer/shredder and of the sampling protocol used. The bulk density of FORBI was found to be 690 kg/m³, while the apparent densities of SRF and RDF were 120kg/m³ and 42Kg/m³ respectively (Casado et al 2016). The average humidity (1.3% w/w), ash (8.3% w/w) and volatiles (76.5% w/w) are on a par with those of SRF (Wagland et al 2016). The concentration of chlorine is rather high (0.45-0.55% w/w). This is expected due to the origin of the material (food residues). The values of gross (19.44 KJ/kg) and net (18.14 KJ/Kg) calorific values, which significantly affect the clinker production rate (Tsiliyannis 2016), are satisfactory for FORBI as a candidate AF. Moreover, the sulfur concentration in FORBI is significantly lower than that of conventional fuels (Table 4).

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Table 4 Elemental analysis, NCV and GCV of FORBI, SRF, RDF, coal and petcoke on dry matter basis

	C (%)	H(%)	N(%)	S (%)	O (%)	Cl (%)	NCV (MJ/Kg)	GCV (MJ/Kg)
FORBI	47.9-48.7	6.16-6.26	2.29-2.31	0.13-0.16	33.0-34.2	0.45-0.55	18.09-18.38	19.32-19.65
SRF (Wagland 2016)	41.8	5.46	0.03	0.07	-	0.02	12.28	13.40
RDF (Wagland 2016)	40.4	4.89	1.41	0.46	-	0.36	20.26	21.26
Coal (Wagland 2016)	70.7	4.48	1.28	1.81	-	0.30	28.50	29.42
Petcoke (Akdag 2016)	68.12	3.63	1.94	4.73	20.5	-	34.38	-

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The total amount of heavy metals in FORBI is low compared to the fuels shown in Table 5, whereas its potassium concentration is ten times that of the one in coal. Nitrogen concentration is almost double that of coal. Notably, Hg, Cd and Tl were not detected in FORBI. These elements are critical in regard to the operating characteristics of clinker production kilns, and to operability constraints (mainly thermal rating of the kiln refractory and flue gas exhaust blower capacity (Tsiliyannis, 2012) as well as to the environmental impacts, which are to be taken into account in a comprehensive evaluation of FORBI. Such an evaluation may take into account new developments in kiln combustion (Tsiliyannis, 2016).

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Table 5 Concentration of metals (mg/Kg) on dry matter basis of FORBI and comparison with SRF, RDF, Coal, petcoke.

	Cd	Hg	Tl	K	Na	Sum (As+Co+Cr+Cu+Sb+Pb+Mn+Ni+V)
FORBI	n.d*	n.d*	n.d*	15,006-16,516	3,738-4,636	49.3-57.4
SRF (Wagland)	0.05	0.07	<0.1	92	247	51.6

2016)						
RDF (Wagland 2016)	0.3	0.19	<0.1	3,454	5,362	329
Coal (Wagland 2016)	0.07	0.3	<0.3	1,845	868	261
Petcoke (Akdag 2016)	-	-	-	-	-	620

214 *not detected

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216 According to the standard EN 15359 2011, the NCV and the chlorine and mercury concentrations are critical indices
 217 used for classification (Table 6). These properties are of interest because the net calorific value serves as an *economic*
 218 *index* as it reflects the thermal efficiency of the fuel. Chlorine concentration is a *technological index* as it quantifies the
 219 risk of corrosion in the combustion chamber and mercury is an *environmental index* because of its likely transfer, as a
 220 volatile compound, to gaseous emissions. FORBI's NCV in the studied samples was 17.96 MJ/kg, its chlorine
 221 concentration (on dry matter) was 0.50% w/w and its mercury concentration below 0.006 mg/MJ.

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Table 6 Classification criteria for alternative solid fuels – EN 15359.

Classification characteristic	Statistic measure	Unit	Class				
			1	2	3	4	5
NCV	Mean	MJ/Kg (ar)	≥25	≥20	≥15	≥10	≥3
Chlorine	Mean	% w/w (d)	≤0.2	≤0.6	≤1.0	≤1.5	≤3
Mercury	Median 80 th percentile	mg/MJ (ar)	≤0.02	≤0.03	≤0.08	≤0.15	≤0.50
		mg/MJ (ar)	≤0.04	≤0.06	≤0.16	≤0.30	≤1.00

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225 Table 7 presents limit values for AFs set by authorities for licensing permits of cement plant in Spain, Belgium and
 226 France (Holcim 2006). Evidently, FORBI is an appropriate AF in all three countries as it falls within the respective limit
 227 values.

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Table 7 Limit values for AFs for different countries based on individual permits (Holcim 2006).

Parameter	Unit	Spain	Belgium	France	FORBI
Halogens (exp .as Cl)	%	2	2	2	0.49
F	%	0.20	-	-	<0.10
S	%	3	3	3	0.14
Hg	mg/Kg	10	5	10	n.d*
Cd	mg/Kg	100	70	-	n.d*
Tl	mg/Kg	100	30	-	n.d*
Sum Hg + Cd + Tl	mg/Kg	100	-	100	n.d*
Sb	mg/Kg	-	200	-	<2.00
Sum(Sb+As+Co+Ni+Pb+Sn+V+Cr)	mg/Kg	5000	2500	2500	18.4
As	mg/Kg	-	200	-	<2.00
Co	mg/Kg	-	200	-	2.13
Ni	mg/Kg	-	1000	-	6.05
Cu	mg/Kg	-	1000	-	7.19
Cr	mg/Kg	-	1000	-	4.25

V	mg/Kg	-	1000	-	<2.00
Pb	mg/Kg	-	1000	-	12.1
Mn	mg/Kg	-	2000	-	21.4
Zn	mg/Kg	-	5000		20.9

230 *not detected

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3.1 Moisture effect and energy requirements for preparation of FORBI

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Food waste moisture levels are at 78%. Final moisture content 15% is the maximum moisture level for classifying the product in Class 3, LHV ≥ 15 MJ / kg. The total energy consumption in kWh/tn for producing FORBI at 1.1%, 5%, 10% and 15% from food waste is shown in Table 8 and Fig. 5. The energy content of FORBI is approximately twice the energy required for its production. Reduced preparation/drying costs will render FORBI more valuable as an AF. For instance, the preparation cost could be reduced if the energy required for drying was obtained by partial use of the product (FORBI) or by waste heat energy recovery within the cement plant.

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Table 8 Drying energy requirements to produce FORBI Class 3- FORBI maximum moisture (for Class 3, LHV ≥ 15 MJ/kg):15%

FW (kg)	FW moisture	FW Dry matter (Kg)	FORBI moisture	Water evaporation (Kg)	FORBI (kg / tn Food waste)	FORBI LHV (MJ/kg)	Energy for water evap. (MJ / kg FORBI)
1000	78%	223	1.1%	775	225	17.9	9.8
1000	78%	223	5.0%	766	234	17.1	9.3
1000	78%	223	10.0%	753	247	16	8.7
1000	78%	223	15.0%	738	262	15	8.0

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Figure 5 Energy requirement to produce FORBI.

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3.2 FORBI's effect on flue gases and fuel mixture

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Two scenarios were considered in order to assess the impact of FORBI in the fuel mixture and in kiln flue gases (preheater gas outflow). Scenario 0 (base case) with a fuel mixture calorific composition of 30% coal, 70% petcoke and Scenario 1 with fuel calorific composition of 30% coal, 50% petcoke, 20% FORBI (1.5% moisture). The quantity of petcoke was reduced from 70% thermal participation in the kiln to 30% thermal participation (i.e. from about 107000 tpa to about 76000 tpa) and the quantity of FORBI was increased, from no contribution to 20% thermal contribution (i.e. from zero to 60000 tpa). Developed in EXCEL software and referring to steady state conditions under either compound or direct operation, the model used to perform the calculations is based on combustion stoichiometry mass balance with 20% excess air and no oxygen enrichment. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the results of the substitution of 20% petcoke with FORBI as an AF in a cement kiln (Scenario 1). Combustion or kiln fluegases refer to the fluegases in the kiln without

255 incorporating CO₂ from lime decomposition. Kiln flue gas mass ratios in Scenario 1 with respect to Scenario 0 of the
 256 following parameters are depicted: Non biogenic CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, HX in Fig. 6 and also mass ratios in Scenario 1 with
 257 respect to Scenario 0 of non volatile metals and of alkalis Na and K, in the entire fuel mixture in Fig. 7. It is apparent
 258 that non biogenic combustion CO₂ due to the fuel mixture is reduced by 20% and also that SO₂ is reduced by about 25%,
 259 while NO_x presence rises by about 20%. The combination of higher alkali presence in the combustion flue gases and
 260 lower sulphur presence favors incombustible alkali deposits on process equipment as alkali chlorides, or incorporation
 261 of alkali chlorides in the clinker mass as salts. This is due to the shift of the chlorine vapor equilibrium to incombustible
 262 alkali halides, under lower SO₂ concentrations or to HCl under higher SO₂ concentrations. A typical ratio is combustible
 263 chlorine/incombustible chlorine =1.5 and therefore this ratio is expected to become lower under petcoke substitution.
 264 Both routes exert detrimental effects either on plant condition and/or on cement quality.

265 Serious concerns arise from chlorine presence in the fuel mixture, which rises by about 60%, a challenge to be
 266 rigorously investigated and appropriate action measures to be identified for efficient FORBI AF utilization, since it
 267 affects offgas emissions of halogens, metals and dioxins (Tsiliyannis 2017; Reijnders 2007) as well as equipment
 268 condition. Alkalis also present a challenge, since their content in the fuel mixture rises by more than 6.5 times, a matter
 269 requiring further investigation in regard to final inclusions and effect on cement product.

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271 **Figure 6** Characterization of FORBI as an AF in cement kilns: petcoke calorific substitution by FORBI: 20%, base case (0):30%
 272 calorific coal, 70% calorific petcoke. Mass ratio of non Biogenic CO₂, SO₂, HX and NO_x in combustion flue gas. m_{fg}: mass in flue
 273 gas mixture in Scenario 1 (30% calorific coal, 50% calorific petcoke, 20% calorific FORBI), m_{fg,0}: mass in flue gas mixture in
 274 Scenario 0 (base case) (30% calorific coal, 70% calorific petcoke).
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277 **Figure 7** Characterization of FORBI as an AF in cement kilns: petcoke calorific substitution by FORBI: 20%, base case (0): 30%
 278 calorific coal, 70% calorific petcoke. Mass ratio of non volatile metals, Na and K in fuel. m_{fuel} / m_{fuel,0} : = mass in fuel mixture in
 279 Scenario 1 (30% calorific coal, 50% calorific petcoke, 20% calorific FORBI) : mass in fuel mixture in Scenario 0 (base case) (30%
 280 calorific coal, 70% calorific petcoke).
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4. Conclusions

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FORBI is classified as a non-dangerous waste according to EWC 20 01 08, European Commission Decision 2014/955. According to EN 15359 it is classified as category 3, 2 and 1 with respect to NCV, Cl and Hg respectively. It is a suitable candidate as a secondary fuel for the cement industry, to given its high calorific value along with its low humidity and ash content. Pipe clogging can be avoided by using FORBI as an AF. The low concentration in heavy metals renders FORBI more favorable from the environmental perspective compared to other AF's. FORBI meets the specifications set by national licensing organizations for cement plants in Spain, Belgium and France. From a thermodynamic point of view, with a level of moisture in FW at 78%, the energy content of FORBI is about twice the energy required for its production.

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In terms of kiln flue gases and fuel mixture, 20% calorific substitution of petcoke by FORBI (1.5% moisture) results in an overall fuel mixture with 80% of the non-volatile metals of the base case and 6.7 times higher K, Na with respect to the base case (Scenario 0). Also, combustion flue gases contain 80% of non-biogenic CO₂ emissions of the base case, 70% of the base case SO₂, 16 times higher HX and 1.2 times higher NO_x compared to the base case (Scenario 0).

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Chlorine content is a major concern in regard to flue gas presence of pollutants. It affects halogen emissions, alkali deposits on process equipment and cement quality. Since most of chlorine is due to food salt, it could be partially removed by mechanical water removal, i.e. via a filter press before drying. In addition removal of chlorines can be realized via addition of activated carbon to the flue gases. Also, the high nitrogen content is a potential disadvantage, mainly, in regard to non-thermal NO_x emissions since, as of 01/01/2016, EU regulations impose new, lower, limits (500 mg/Nm³ instead of 800 mg/Nm³). There exist, however, techniques for the reduction of NO_x: either using low-NO_x furnaces or with catalytic or non-catalytic stripping from the flue gases. The energy demands for the drying process of food waste are high, especially for a 78% moisture content of food waste. This energy could be cut by more than one third via mechanical dewatering of food waste prior to drying. Techniques for reducing drying costs are important and should be further investigated including partial use of the product (FORBI) as a dryer fuel and low temperature waste heat recuperation within the plant.

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Acknowledgements

Present work is produced under research project Horizon 2020, Grand Agreement No 688995. «Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems-[WASTE4THINK].

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